

Academic Organizational Culture

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Abstract:- In the academic field, functional structures are the fundamental entities on the basis of which the current system is developed and reformed. In this case, we are dealing not with simple administrative structures representative of the other types of education system, but we are talking about official departments, which form the structure of the faculty. Generically, coordinators are appointed heads of department. Cumulatively, the totality of departments forms the structure of the faculty. Subsequently, the sum of all these sectors forms the academic ensemble. The management is formed by an executive office that includes those authorized and elected persons at central level, from different environments of activity, but who are part of the organization, but also the central coordinator called rector. These units represent school structures that are not centrally administered, compared to the preschool system or at the high school level. Each entity represents an individual legal personality that is centrally administered and opts for its own choices, being autonomously responsible for the rules, conduct or organization to which it is subject. The modus operandi of these organizations is not an institutional one, being a multidirectional operational coordination that depends on the entire group of persons in management positions such as the deans, vice-deans, the executive office and the rectors.

Keywords:- Academic Environment; University; Leadership; Culture; Organization.

I. INTRODUCTION

From a strictly communicative point of view, the organizational culture of the academic environment can be regarded as the result of all actions, individual and organizational behaviors that have led or lead to the modification of the behavior of the people who are the object of activity of the organization. At the same time, the attitude that outsiders assimilate is made up of the sum of organizational representations, that is, the individual sum of all faculties included in the academy, but also towards the academy as a totally hoped-for entity, from a legal point of view.

Although the university environment has the freedom to administer itself individually, this does not imply a total independence from the competent bodies. They have freedom of action within the limits of the law established by the competent authorized bodies and governing the entire process at central level. The highest level of this sector is represented

by the Ministry of Education, an organization that aims to develop and improve education. It also ensures the overall coordination of education [1].

Thus, academic identity must be formed under the image of higher bodies, in order not to create divergences from a legislative point of view. The image of the organization results from its own presentation of the events, of the created public, of the messages transmitted, of the activities carried out but also of the problems that may appear on this plan. Thus, the relations maintained by the academy with the private environment, with the public environment and with the official authorities of this field directly and substantially affect the image and culture that is cultivated within the organization.

However, culture must be unique within these organizations to create differentiation and uniqueness. Both the elements of differentiation and the fundamental features of the organization must be distinguishable, but be assimilated as constants. The developed culture must be used to describe the internal events of the organization, to reflect the behavior adopted. Both educationally and professionally.

II. MATERIALS

Although the academic environment is predominantly public in Europe, attitudes and strategies are aimed at behavior oriented towards private agents. This occurs because there is a high level of competition in the education market, which is not a quantification of financial profit, but of people inserted into the labor market. In this situation, the degree of culture that supports the organizational image can decisively lead to results recorded by it.

For this reason, setting and setting clear objectives for the behavior adopted is vital. Confrontations with various problems can occur both individually, at the level of representatives, and from an organizational point of view. In both cases it is a question of direct and indirect integration of problems that can alter the organizational image. Basically, from the perspective of methodological individualism, the organization is represented by the sum of the individuals it represents. This approach must be taken into account in the analysis of the organizational culture.

A lack of timing or a different evaluation of the set of rules of conduct and organizational deontological rules, in relation to administrative persons and those in management positions, can affect the entire group. Basically, the image of a department or a faculty, once it undergoes changes as a result of events that

negatively change the perception of the public, will most likely lead to an escalation of problems. The public's perception towards a certain part of the academic environment viewed as a whole will change the perception of the entire organization [1].

For these reasons, it is necessary to form a strong organizational culture in academia of three established elements. The first time is about the control imposed by the executive office of the academy. It must give clear instructions and rules regarding the authority that the other members of the organization have. It must be drawn out, it must be clearly delineated the power that they exercise from other persons, it must be clearly specified what is the area in which a particular person has the necessary skills to act and what that level is.

These elements are part of the planning and programming function, which involves designing and providing for the content of a clear organizational chart and a set of rules voted on, authorized, to be recognized as a legislative act in itself. Although this does not require a full planning plan, the objectives set annually or quarterly must be carried out with a finite number of people and trained or oriented towards a specific field of activity [2]. Achieving objectives can only be achieved through the clear and direct attribution of objectives. In case of contract there is a possibility of confusion at internal level, which would lead to an erroneous perception of the organizational culture.

It should be noted that in the case of the academy, the outside audience is inside the organization, being mainly about students. The importance of this stems from the need for permanent organization and coordination of employees [1].

The stability of the image as well as the validation of the organizational identity in the eyes of the public is closely related to the transmission and perpetuation of the values and beliefs that make up the organizational culture. Image validation and maintenance is achieved through the methods of solving problems that occur frequently and that involuntarily test the organization's ability to cope with pressures.

Cultivated culture is a complex mechanism at the core of which are the people who relate and who most often have contact with the public. The culture promoted within the company, i.e. the internal one, is determined by the rules imposed by the management and is also the one that supports an organization, representing the strongest cohesion force and which allows the members the stability and predictability necessary to modify the working mechanisms [3].

Secondly, it is about the communication models adopted and imposed through the organizational culture. Specifically, it is about the extent to which organizational communications are restricted from communicating with the formal hierarchical authority. The framework is formed due to the repeated interactions between the members of the groups of the organization, the bringing together of the beliefs and values of the individuals they form. For this reason, it is a uniform imposition of the conduct that takes place within the company [4].

Most academic environments have reached the age of maturity, the exceptions being formed by private organizations, new ones emerging in this segment. Precisely for this reason, it is necessary for people who appear after the period of maturity, development of organizational culture, to be educated, to be presented with the concepts and the imposed deontological rules. In the contrary case, given the multitude of faculties that make up the academic environment as a whole, there is a high possibility of creating a differentiation from the image. This will automatically lead to confusion among external audiences [5].

Another third most important such and one of the decisive factors of organizational culture in represent identity. Each individual and every organization under the organization of academia as a superior leadership mechanism must identify with the general organizational culture.

Otherwise, the support cannot take place in a common manner, the coordinators will not be able to centrally regulate the activities and a clear and useful communication activity will not be provided for the other members of the group [6].

Individual and group goals should be consistent with the organization's long-term goals. Moreover, not only the objectives set must be respected, but especially the new ones, the goals that appear unannounced, which develop during the activity, must be in balance with the long-term ones. This can only be achieved by identifying individual and common objectives. Although this cannot be done in a total manner, it is preferable that the extent to which this takes place should be as great as possible [5].

III. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the functional perspective on the organization goes through the individual plans of the people inside it. Organizational culture is not an abstract element. Even though it cannot be quantifiable, it determines the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization and can affect the entire object of activity. Strong cultures often have a fairly high degree of rigidity and inflexibility, which is influenced both by the number of people active within the organization, but also by the age that the organization itself has.

An upgrade or alignment of the value system can only be achieved through a uniform change in the principles and objectives. It is preferable for this change to come from within the organization, in this case it is a question of anticipation of possible problems that can restrict the image and affect the organizational culture.

In order to be more efficient and to ensure a more optimal implementation of the basic principles of the adopted culture, it is preferable that the rules be clearly outlined, the academic objectives to be uniform and realistic and, most importantly, to achieve a compromise between the individual needs at the faculty level and the organizational ones at the central level by the central executive office.

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